

THE ENIGMA OF PAK-AFGHAN RELATIONS: ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Pak-Afghan relations have entered a new phase of transition for the first time in the history of both the countries. The earlier blame game has taken the form of direct confrontation and open war whereby the two countries have been faced with hundreds of death casualties and injuries besides loss to the infrastructure. The regional dynamics have also tried to bring an end to the war and reach out a viable solution to the conflict but of no avail. The changing security dynamics at the global level coupled with the resultant US-Iran conflict and the role of Pakistan as a peace mediator have also focused the world's eyes to the leading role of Pakistan in the regional and international politics. This study aims at exploring the enigma of the Pak-Afghan relations and the subsequent issues and challenges faced by Pakistan. Main findings of the study testify that the repatriation of the Afghan refugees by the Pakistani authorities, the May 2025 Pak-India conflict, Pakistan's leading role in the regional politics and the Afghan proxy war have further ignited the Pak-Afghan relations leading to the worsening of the law and order situation along the border sides.

INTRODUCTION

Pak-Afghan relations are faced with tough situation in the present arena on account of their involvement in open confrontation for the first time in the history. Earlier, there had been verbal blame game between the two neighboring countries but now the blame game has taken a practical manifestation. Some of the issues have led to the worsening of relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan passing through many ups and downs in their political history. One of the main reasons for their conflict is the Pak-Afghan border over which the two countries has different stance with regard to its validity as an international border. Some of the insurgent elements have been launching offensive to deteriorate the relations between the two countries (Aleks Phillips, 2026). The border covers an area of 2,600 km (1, 615 miles), connecting some of the key provinces of both the countries (Aleks Phillips, 2026). Provinces of Afghanistan bordering Pakistan include Nangarhar, Nuristan, Kunar, Khost, Paktia, and Paktika that are normally used by the non-state actors for infiltration and worsening of law and order situation along the border areas (Aleks Phillips, 2026).

Recently relations between the countries have worsened to such a great extent that both of them stood against each other in direct confrontation resulting in the death casualties besides destruction of the infrastructure (Aleks Phillips, 2026). Taliban have been relying predominantly on commercially drones carrying improvised explosive devices (IEDs) making their range and targeting capabilities (Aleks Phillips, 2026). Round about 22 military sites of the non-state actors living in Afghanistan have been targeted by the law enforcement agencies of Pakistan including Kabul and Kandahar while great care has been taken to avoid civilian casualties (Aleks Phillips, 2026). The number of death casualties

and injuries on both sides of the Pak-Afghan border differ as per estimates of the different sources and web pages.

During the recent Pak-Afghan confrontation, at least 274 Afghan Taliban have been killed, while destroying 73 posts inside Afghanistan besides capturing 18 posts (Aleks Phillips, 2026). An estimated 115 tanks, armored vehicles and artillery systems were also destroyed during the conflict. Twelve Pakistani soldiers have lost their lives while 27 being injured in the conflict. The recent ongoing conflict between Afghanistan and Pakistan has resulted in the death of 583 Afghan fighters and 795 injured, alongside the destruction of 242 checkpoints. The conflict has caused casualties on both sides of the border including the death and injuries to the law enforcement agencies of Pakistan. The Taliban government has also reported the death of 58 Pakistani soldiers, and 30 personnel being injured in the conflict (Ali, 2025).

As far as the Pak-Afghan conflict is concerned, each side has been blaming the other for the worsening situation by attacking first and inflicting heavy losses on the other side (Aleks Phillips, 2026). Prime Minister of Pakistan, Shahbaz Sharif said that his country's forces were able to crush aggression while Defense Minister of Pakistan declared "open war" on Taliban in Afghanistan (Aleks Phillips, 2026). During the confrontation, the Iranian government offered to mediate between the two countries but the situation took a more serious turn when Iran was struck by the United States and Israel on 28th February 2026 (Lutz Kilian, 2026). China that counts itself to be friendly to both Pakistan and Afghanistan called for a ceasefire with the foreign ministry spokesman Mao Ning urging them to "remain calm and exercise restraint" (Aleks Phillips, 2026). While Foreign Secretary of the UK Yvette Cooper echoed calls for both sides to engage in

mediated dialogues, adding that the two should “take immediate steps toward de-escalation” and “avoid further harm to civilians” (Aleks Phillips, 2026).

There is a greater need for the countries to ease tension and avoid further confrontation in future (Tariq, Pak-Afghan Stalemate: Search for Rapprochement, 2026) . UN Human Rights Chief, Volker Turk urged Pakistani military and Afghan *de facto* security personnel to end fighting and prioritize helping the millions who depend on aid and whose lives have been tormented by violence and misery for a long time (Shamdasani, 2026). Civilians on both sides of the border have been trying to flee from the airstrikes, heavy artillery fire, mortar shelling and gunfire, (Shamdasani, 2026). Turk opines that he has been pleading with all parties to bring an end to the conflict and prioritize helping those experiencing extreme hardship (Shamdasani, 2026) . In 2025, the United Nations attributed 87 death casualties and 518 injuries in Afghanistan to Pakistani military forces, the highest number of civilian death casualties ascribed to cross-border attacks in a single year since 2009 (Shamdasani, 2026) . Since the start of the year, 69 civilians have been killed and 141 injured in Afghanistan (Shamdasani, 2026).

The repatriation of the Afghan refugees initiated by the government of Pakistan in September 2023 has resulted in the repatriation of over two million Afghan refugees to their parent country (Tariq, 2026). Almost another two million Afghan refugees are believed to remain in Pakistan, where most of them face constant fear of arrest and deportation (Shamdasani, 2026) . Turk is of the view that as a result of the violence, humanitarian assistance cannot reach many of those desperately in need, causing misery over misery (Shamdasani, 2026) . About 22 million people in Afghanistan, equal to half of the population of Afghanistan needs humanitarian assistance, including over 11.6 million children. The airstrikes in Afghanistan came after a series of

deadly incidents

in Pakistan this year, including an assault on a checkpoint in Bajaur, suicide bombings of Shi’a mosque in Islamabad and at a wedding ceremony in Dera Ismail Khan and other attacks (Shamdasani, 2026) . Turk urges that the cycle of retaliation and violence adds to the worries and sufferings of the people living across both sides of the border. He further opines that he urges both Pakistan and Afghanistan to de-escalate and address the security issues they face through dialogue, negotiation and mutual cooperation (Shamdasani, 2026).

With the world’s eyes focused on war in Iran, another conflict goes along the eastern border of Iran since February 28, 2026. Due to the official declaration of war, between Afghanistan and Pakistan, the fighting in Iran drew little attention (Shamdasani, 2026) . But the emerging position of Pakistan during the recent US-Iran conflict provided Pakistan with an opportunity to play the role of a mediator for resolving the conflict (BIBERMAN, 2026) . Prolongation of the Pak-Afghan war would bring consequences for the shaping of the region in future (BIBERMAN, 2026). Beijing’s alliance with Pakistan and New Delhi’s growing influence over the current government of Afghanistan have turned border skirmishes into regional conflict affecting the neighboring countries.

Since the retake of Afghanistan by Taliban in August 2021, relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan have remained very rocky. The proximate cause of the war between the two neighboring states was that Pakistan’s stance over its northern border is harboring the Tehrik-e-Taliban Pakistan, a non-state actor that has plagued Islamabad and was responsible for the massacre of Peshawar School attack on 16th December, 2014 resulting in the death of 144 people, mostly children (BIBERMAN, 2026) . During the first term of the Afghan Taliban regime in Afghanistan during 1996-2001 relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan remained

friendly and cordial but the post-9/11 scenario created security risks inside Pakistan to such an extent that resulted in the huge growth of the non-state actors whereby the state of Pakistan had to sign peace deals with the non-state actors and upon failure of the peace parleys, the state had to launch military operations against the outlaws and insurgents.

Pakistan's Concern over Afghanistan

Pakistan has been more concerned in Afghanistan's becoming as a proxy of India (BIBERMAN, 2026). During the first phase of Taliban in power during 1996-2001 relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan remained more normal and cordial on account of Taliban's relations with the government of Pakistan (Tariq, 2026). But the recent ties between Afghanistan and India have been viewed with great concern by Islamabad particularly when both Pakistan and India entered into direct confrontation in May 2025. Now, the Taliban regime in Afghanistan is posing threat to the security paradigm of Pakistan since the Taliban regime in Kabul is enjoying cordial relations with New Dehli. In such a scenario, Pakistan's reservations on both the eastern and the western borders may pose more security concerns for it, rather the fear of being sandwiched by the countries (BIBERMAN, 2026). It is pertinent to mention here that for India, fostering closer ties with the Taliban regime would carry double benefits of improving its hands against Pakistan as well as preventing future inflows of Islamist militants from Afghanistan into Kashmir, the disputed Himalayan region having claimed by both India and Pakistan (BIBERMAN, 2026).

But it is also significant that China's role in the region is also gaining more and more momentum particularly in context of its relations with Pakistan and its rivalry with India, most notably marked by their border issues during 1962 (BIBERMAN, 2026). China's friendly relations with Pakistan have also been of good omen for Pakistan because Pakistan's unfriendly

relations with eastern and western neighbors also lead to increased tension in the region. In the wake of changing security dynamics, India and Afghanistan may move towards Pakistan but China is a time tested friend of Pakistan and has always been there with Pakistan in times of crisis and external conflict. Situation went more in favor of Pakistan when China began to replace the United States as Pakistan's closest military partner, giving more strength and alliance to Pakistan in the region.

Moreover, Islamabad-Beijing faced a test in May 2025 during Operation Shindoor, whereby India had to carry out limited military operation inside Pakistan in response to terrorist attacks on its territory. During the conflict, Chinese intelligence, air defense infrastructure, and reportedly Chengdu J-10C "Vigorous Dragon" fighter jets gave a very surprising edge to Pakistan. Pertinent to mention that Chinese material not only proved its worth during the conflict but also helped effectively in changing the nature of the Pak-India conflict. The war between Pakistan and Afghanistan makes the first glimpse of the new security landscape of South Asia and the Central Asia since no direct war has been fought between the two countries in the past. It has been considered as the first sustained encounter between the initial ally of India, Afghanistan and the western ally of China's military friend, Pakistan (BIBERMAN, 2026).

Urmqi Talks

Many efforts and diplomatic missions tried their hands to bridge over the gap between Pakistan and Afghanistan. One of such efforts, the Urmqi talks, was hosted in April by China, tried to bring the delegates from both Pakistani and Afghanistan together for the first time in February and March since the conflict's most intense phase (Hussain, 2026). The discussion was welcomed by both sides and was highly appreciated by Kabul calling it as 'useful' while Pakistan also appreciated to such an extent that

further progress would depend on Kabul (Hussain , 2026). Though the talks received great applause from both sides and the regional community but no agreement was reached at between the two countries. Pakistan has been accusing the Afghan Taliban of providing sanctuaries to the Pakistani Taliban, the Tehrike-Taliban (TTP) emerged in 2007 in Pakistan in the aftermath of the 9/11 syndrome and the resultant military operations (Hussain , 2026). Afghanistan has been rejecting these accusations and consequently makes Pakistan responsible for interference in the internal affairs of Afghanistan. Both have been urging each other to enter into written agreement that could help the two countries bring an end to the war and enter a new era of peace and stability but still no fruitful agreement has been reached out.

Moreover, the United Nations have also urged both Pakistan and Afghanistan to declare a fresh ceasefire and peace agreement following the ignition of the ongoing conflict in February 2026 and the collapse of the October 2025 ceasefire (UN, 2026). The United Nations experts further opines that, “We urge Pakistan and the *de facto* Afghan authorities to commit to a permanent ceasefire, resolve the root causes of conflict, and ensure accountability for violations of international law” (Hussain , 2026) . Since 26 February 2026, there have been at least 289 civilian casualties in Afghanistan, including 76 killings and 213 injures, with over 115,000 people having been displaced. Civilian infrastructure has been damaged, including medical facilities, homes, markets, and sites for displaced people. Schools and borders have been closed and trade suspended (Hussain , 2026).

The experts and peace mediators have also urged the parties to respect the international law, including the protection of civilians and civilian objects (Hussain , 2026). They have been calling for prompt, independent and transparent investigations of all alleged violations by the perpetrators and providing the victims with

remedies and ransom as per international law (Hussain , 2026). Peace is for the best interest of both the states and would lead to harmonize the relations between the two states, besides catering for peace and stability in the region. It is in the best interest of the two states to take to task the non-state actors working within their respective countries and impose strict surveillance against those found of violating and committing the acts of perpetration. All authorities including the Taliban need to prevent terrorist groups like the Tehrik-e-Taliban Pakistan from threatening the human right to life, including their own frontiers (Hussain , 2026).

Pakistan’s Role in Afghanistan

Taliban are trying to maintain cordial relations with the neighboring counties, and the group has maintained a higher level of diplomatic ties than it did during 1990s while in power (Thomas, 2026). The recent regime of the Taliban has a different diplomatic strategy with regard to the regional and global politics where Russia became the first country to recognize the Taliban regime in July 2025 whereas in 1990s three countries recognized the Taliban government (Thomas, 2026) . But the role of Pakistan has always been crucial in shaping the politics of Afghanistan particularly in the wake of the Russian withdrawal from Afghanistan in 1988 and the invasion of the United States and its allied partners in 2001 in the aftermath of the 9/11 scenario. In both of the cases, Pakistan played an active part in the regional politics on account of its geostrategic position in the world affairs. A glaring example of it is the holding of meetings with the new Taliban government in Afghanistan, both in Kabul and Islamabad since the retake of the country by the Afghan Taliban in August 2021 (Thomas, 2026).

Challenges for Pakistan

The Taliban’s return to power in August 2021 has been viewed by the regional actors from many perspectives; including both challenging and opportunities. For a country like Pakistan,

the Taliban government has many challenges in the regional and global politics (Thomas, 2026). The Taliban's victory has given a morale and likely material boost to Pakistan-based Tehrik-e-Taliban (TTP), a US-designated Foreign Terrorist Organization (Thomas, 2026). In the aftermath of the August 2021, attacks by the TTP against the Pakistani security agencies increased creating internal security crises in Pakistan. Security became a matter of great concern for both the countries to such an extent that the two countries have to enter into direct confrontation. Sporadic cross-border clashes between Taliban and Pakistani Forces over the past two years escalated in February 2026 into an 'open war' (Thomas, 2026).

The open war between Pakistan and Afghanistan led the regional dynamics to initiate negotiations for peace and reconciliation. Till now, all the efforts taken in this regard have not reached any fruitful result while security situation along both sides of the border has worsened with deterioration of law and order situation. Moreover, Pakistan-Afghanistan relations are further complicated by the repatriation of the Afghan refugees to their parent country by the Pakistani authorities launched in February 2023 including 900,000 in 2025 alone (Thomas, 2026). The military operations and counter-insurgency moves by the United States in the post-9/11 scenario has also helped in strengthening the relations between the Taliban-Al-Qaeda for decades. The sanctions by the UN, the US and other donor agencies are some of the other contributory factors in bringing all on-state actors on a joint platform and fighting against the state machinery.

Discussion and Conclusion

Since the retake of Afghanistan in August 2021 Pakistan and Afghanistan have been facing a very deteriorating security situation. For the first time in the history of the two states, they have entered into direct and open war while creating another dilemma for the people living across both

sides of the border who are tied by relations of blood, business and trade activities besides being tied by the common religion of being Muslims. Earlier, both the countries only were busy in a blame game, each blaming the rival for the current law and order situation across both the sides of the border and border infiltration. But the situation took a very practical manifestation when both the neighboring countries go engaged in direct war against each, which was further infuriated by the repatriation of the Afghan refugees to their parent country by the Pakistani authorities. Though most of the Afghan refugees have been repatriated to their country yet they had also to show resistance and unwillingness to return to their country and preferred to reside in Pakistan but the strong determination of the Pakistani authorities compelled them to abide by the law of the host country.

Most of the worsening security situation between the two countries is the validity of the Pak-Afghan border which the Afghan people don't recognize as an international border though the ruling class from time to time recognized it as an international border. Pakistan, being successor to the British government, abides by the law of the transfer of power during by the British government to the Pakistani government and independence plan of 1947 leading to the separation of India and Pakistan, claims it to be an international border. This divergence in the opinion of the two states over the validity of the Pak-Afghan border add further to the worsening of the law and order situation and cross border infiltration. Moreover, the Soviet intervention in Afghanistan in 1979 and resultant withdrawal in 1988 and the post-9/11 syndrome has also created power vacuum, leadership crisis and internal civil war in inside Afghanistan where the stakeholders are no given proper representation in the governmental set up of the country.

The neighboring countries and regional dynamics need to play the role of a peace

negotiator and help resolve the issue once for all. Many efforts were made entering into peace and reconciliation through diplomacy and table talks but nothing substantial has yet been reached out. China, has been trying to help resolve issue but since now, no peace agreement has been reached between the two countries. One such reason for failure to reach into peace agreement is the proximity of relation of relations between Afghanistan and India. Moreover, the Pak-India conflict in May 2025 is another itching point in their relations since India has been trying to override Pakistan from both sides of the eastern and western borders. But Pakistan's friendly relations with is giving more leverage to Pakistan in the region as China is a time tested friend of Pakistan.

The repatriation of the Afghan refugees by the government of Pakistan has also been viewed as a contributing factor towards the worsening of the Pak-Afghan relations resulting in the ongoing conflict. The Afghani people are unwilling to return to their countries on the plea of having spent almost 46 years in Pakistan while Pakistani government has been urging the Afghan people to return to their countries since peace and stability prevails in Afghanistan. Moreover, the presence of the Afghan refugees has now been an extra burden on the exchequer of the Pakistani government as their presence in the country not only caters for the accommodation but also the use of the resources besides education and health facilities coupled with all the daily commodities. Keeping in view the extra burden on the exchequer of the Afghani people on the government of Pakistan, peace and stability in Afghanistan in the current scenario and the world's eyes focused on the war in Iran, the government of Pakistan and Afghanistan should take joint action for the resolution of the border dispute, resolving the issue of non-state actors, the repatriation of the Afghan refugees and the need for peace and stability in the region as their top most priority.

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